

WORK LIFE BALANCE OF EMPLOYEES AT KARANJA INDUSTRIES PVT LTD BIDAR

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ABSTRACT

Since he became Hollander, the batter was developed around 1750 and adopted in the Netherlands. In 1799, Frenchman Robert invented the process of forming paper on a moving screen. In the process of evolution and improvement, it became today's longest paper machine. In 1809, Dickson invented the cylinder and forced Fourdrinier into the background, but in 1830, fourdrinier's superiority was established for the production of fine paper. In 1826, steam cylinders were used for drying, and Fourdrinier was received in the United States in 1827. Due to lower prices, higher level of general education and increased demand for papermaking. The deceived company developed by the Keller Company of Saxony developed a process machinery to produce wood pulp, but the quality of paper produced was low. In 1909, the sulphate process was introduced in the United States. This process led the paper industry in 1981.

1.1 INTRODUCTION:

As the population increases, the demand for paper is very large. This demand has greatly increased the main raw materials for the paper industry; pulp from woody plants and the pulp industry and paper converted into paper and its products.

Trees are non-renewable resources, the continuous use of trees for the purpose of producing paper will destroy forests and create environmental imbalances, so we thought of alternative ways to minimize the use of trees by purpose, so the idea of recycling is born waste paper, paper and paper products, will reduce to a minimum 30% to 40% of the use of trees for the manufacture of paper. The karanja industries pvt ltd. It is also one that uses papers to be recycled and recycles it on board duplex, craft board.

Writing paper comes from a tall cane papyrus growing along the Nile River in Egypt. The tape sticks to the starch. This time it was superior to calfskin and goatskin. Wax boards and other writing materials that were available at the time. The Chinese invented a very good process to produce high-quality paper by hand today. Southern Europe has learned about this process and began manufacturing rags around the 17th century. In 1960, a paper mill was established in the United States. Throughout Europe, paper mills are made from cotton and rags. The printing of this book began with the Gutenberg Bible. Which greatly increased the demand for paper.

1.2 INDUSTRY PROFILE:

Paper is an integral part of everyday life. Paper is one of the important economic indicators of a country. Today, life cannot be imagined without paper. Paper pervades all sectors of our activity from books to bullets and from morning news paper to nuclear technology. Paper remains the dominant and essential vehicle of modern communications.

Paper is a basic medium of communication and dissemination of information. It helps all the human beings for the growth of education, reading, writing, storing, knowledge, quality of life, culture and other sectors of the economy. Modern man / women starts his / her daily activities with morning news paper and his / her activity ends with writing of diary at night. Kids to things are using paper either directly or indirectly. It is very difficult to imagine modern life without paper. The perception consumption of paper is often regarded as a barometer of socio-economic progress of a country. Paper measures the living standards and living standards and openers of a society and its educational and intellectual attainments.

ORIGIN OF PAPER:

Etymologically, 'paper' is derived from Latin word 'Papyrus' and French word 'papier' a web composed of vegetable fibre, roughly, oriented and matter together to form sheet. 'Papyrus' is a kind of grass. A material of Egyptian origin that was extensively used by the Greco-Roman world. Paper denotes a deposit of vegetable fibre, prepared from an aqueous suspension. It consists of a sheet made by pasting together thin sections of an Egyptian reed (Cyperus papyrus) of the sedge family, a plant which grew in abundance in the delta of Nile river in Egypt. Paper can be defined as a sheet continuous web of material formed by the deposition of vegetable, mineral, animal or synthetic fibers or mixtures with or without the addition of other substance into liquid vapour, or gas in such way that the fibres are intermeshed together.

GLOBAL PAPER INDUSTRY:

The paper industry has realized a linkage between production of paper and the farming community there by infusing huge capital in agricultural economy in the globe. The USA, Latin America, Scandinavian countries, Australia, Japan and neighbouring countries viz, China, Indonesia etc have been quick to create conducive land / forestry policies to encourage large scale production plantations and attract mega investments in pulp and paper / paper board manufacturing and in the process, creating millions of job. The paper industry is largely dominated by the United States, Canada, Sweden, Finland, Japan, Australia, and Latin America. In addition to being one of the dominating force in the industry, the United States also consumes more paper than any other country in the world.

1.3 COMPANY PROFILE:

Kraft equipment is located in 106 is part of a 36-acre site in the village of Sindbandgi. The company can try to install kraft production units in 2000 with a production capacity of 200,000 tons per day. Then expanded to 50 tons per day, during the 2011-12 period. The kraft unit again with it has expanded capacity of 750,000 ton Karanja Industrial pvt. Established in march 1983. The registered capital is rs.50,000,000/-

according to the company law of 1956, the production of 5000 tons of white double-sided panel. Since 1996, the company has passed FSC and ISO 9001:2008 Certification. The paper industry is driving strong demand and expanding sentiment to meet the expected demand of 8 million tons in 2011 and 13 million tons according to India's paper industry is one of the 15 major countries in the world today. its annual output exceeds demand of 8 million tons, and its turnover is expected to reach 1.5 billion rupees. A large number of capacity expansion and expansion plans have been announced and 10,000 diamonds have been districted in various industries including paper cardboard and newspapers India's economy is progressing smoothly and goal is to achieve growth of more than 8% with economic reforms and liberalised government policies, in the today represents an excellent investment opportunity. One of the first foreign direct investment projects can adopt a proposed finish proposal to establish a capacity plant with an annual capacity of 400,000 tons/year and an investment of US\$240 million

Since energy costs account for almost 25% of production costs, there is an urgent need to improve energy management and energy consumption.

The leap in production quality required by demand forecasting is only possible through the expansion of existing capabilities. Gradual changes in technology and new features also involve significant investment. The use of agricultural waste for pulp production also involves challenges such as pollution control, recycling, and the use of economically beneficial technologies for agricultural waste.

s per day. The unit is equipped with all the advanced facilities such as raw materials, finished papers, and electric rooms. In addition, we recently completed the establishment of E.T. under the conditions established by KSPCB Bangalore with an investment of approximately rs and a zero emission system 50/-shellac includes three tanks for screening SS, clarifiers and several troughs needed for this purpose instead we use a 10-ton. Thermax boiler to meet equipment consumption. our unit also likes to have side sugar units, from where we are taking sugarcane bagasse to use our boilers, which are less expensive than thermal coal or other fuels for the local advantages of the factory.

2.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY:

Work life balance

The term work life balance was coined in 1986 in America (Lockwood, 2003) and it became popular in 1990's because of the book named 'The Overworked American, The Unexpected Decline of Leisure' written by Juliet Schor's (1991). The book illustrates how the changing pattern of employment has created so many demands on people that they very little time for leisure (Guest, 2002), it has been identified that factors contributing to increased in work life balance issues are rising competition, aging workforce, sophisticated technology, increasing dual income families along with greater number of women entering in the workforce.

Definition:

Work life balance is a broad concept involving proper prioritizing between “work” on one hand and “life” on another the term work life balance is sometimes used interchanging with the term work-family balance. However, the later term is very limited in its scope including only the responses of work and family.

Theories of work life balance

According to Zedek and Mosier (1990) and O’ Driscoll (1996) ‘there are typically five main models used to explain the relationship between work and life outside work .

Segmentation model:

According to this model work and non work are two distinct domains of life which have no influence on one another and are lived separately this model appears to have a theoretical possibility without any empirical support. at

Spill over model:

Spill over model postulates that work and non work can influence one another either in positive or negative way. Although a lot of research is done on this model, stil a detailed analysis regarding causes, nature and consequences of spill over is done on this model, still a detailed analysis regarding causes nature and consequences of spill over is required to be studied.

Instrumental model:

Instrumental model postulates that one segment facilities success in other segment.

Measurement of work life balance

The work life balance is measured using variety of scale developed by researchers. Fisher (2001) developed a scale that measures work life balance in terms of three dimensions namely;

- Work interference with personal life ; (WIPL) occurs when duties and responsibilities at work make it difficult to fulfil family responsibilities.
- Personal life interference with work (PLIW);PLIW occurs when family duties and responsibilities make it difficult to fulfil work responsibilities.
- Work/personal life enhancement: work/personal life enhancement involves positive impact of work on personal life and personal life on work.

Fisher (2001) further suggested that work life balance consists of four components. They are

1. Time.
2. Behaviour

3. Strain
4. Energy

- Personal and social needs: personal and social needs include exercise, hobbies, recreational activities.
- Time management: time management signifies the ability of an individual to balance time demands between work and personal life.
- Team work: team work is measured by the work environment and culture prevailing at work place.
- Organizational benefits and support: this dimension includes benefits and support offered by organization to employees.
- Type of work: this includes the type of work to be performed by the employee.

Importance of work life balance

In the current scenario, due to increasing work pressure, globalization and technological advancement, working professionals are finding it very difficult to attain the desired level of work life balance. Due to the vast progress taking place in information and communication technology employees have to follow fixed schedules, strict deadlines and rising corporate targets in order to survive in today's competitive business environment. Thus making work life balance the need of the hour. Hobson, Delunas and kesic (2001) illustrated individual, societal and organizational consequences of work life imbalance. They are

- Individual and societal consequences
 - Increased level of stress and health illness.
 - Decreased life satisfaction.
 - Higher incidence of family disputes, violence and divorce.
 - Rising rate of drug abuse.
 - Rising problems with parenting and supervision of children and adolescents.
 - Escalating rates of juvenile delinquency and violence.
- Organizational consequences;
 - Increased rates of turnover and absenteeism.
 - Decreased productivity.
 - Reduced job satisfaction.
 - Decreased organizational commitment and loyalty towards organization.
 - Increasing healthcare cost.

Outcomes of work life balance for the employees:

- Increased employee's wellbeing and happiness.
- Improved relations with management.
- Improved employee's self-esteem, health, concentration, and confidence.

- Increased marital satisfaction and life satisfaction.
- Tasks are managed better.
- Reduction in the level of stress and related illness.

Outcomes of work life balance for the employer:

- Maximized available labour.
- The balance makes employees feel valuable.
- Less stressful work environment.
- Work life balance practice.
- Loyal and motivated workforce.
- Reduced absenteeism and turnover.
- Improved job performances

2.2 LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Wickham and Fishwick (2008)

Reported that organisations need to maintain a detail account of employees work and non work roles and activities so as to effectively manage their work life balance initiatives.

2. Albertsen et al (2008)

Reported that female employees who workrd for higher number of work hours and engaged in overtime work experienced low work life balance in their life. This observation was also found to exist among gender mixed groups.

3. Buddhapriya (2009)

Reported that women professionals at middle management and senior management level considered their commitment to family duties and repsonsibilities as the most important barrier to their making advancements in their career.

4. McLellan and Uys (2009)

Reported that self employed women identified their ability to balance their work life and family life as a result of their organisational ability to structure their daily routine and planning of activities.

5. Waumsley et al (2010)

Stated that women employees who have children experience more work family conflict than work life conflict. On the contrary women employees who do not have children experience more work life conflict and less work family conflict in comparison to their counterparts who have children.

6. Doble and Supriya (2010)

Found that in IT companies in india, both men and women preferred flexible working hours and home working as options to improve their work life balance.

7. Morganson et al (2010)

Found that home based teleworkers experienced high level of work life balance support and job satisfaction than client based workers. However home based teleworkers experienced similar levels of work life balance support and job satisfaction like the main office workers.

8. Sharma and Mehta (2011)

Reported that employees working as area sales managers experienced serious work life imbalance because of extreme sales pressure. The area sales manager has a fiercely has a competitive job and has to travel extensively. Therefore it is an extremely high pressure job and results in work life imbalance.

9. Delicta (2011)

Stated that work environment is more responsible in comparison to the family environment for crating imbalance in a workers professional and personal life. Investing more time on job related leads to the worker experiencing lower family satisfaction.

10. Downes and Koekemoer (2011)

Reported that employees felt that the use of flexible time for work gave them the psychological benefit of experiencing less stress and anxiety. Improved work life balance made them feel related, happy and enhanced their energy level at the workplace.

11. Kasthuri and Rajkumar (2011)

Stated that in India female workers are the worst sufferers due to imbalance in work and family segments. Although Maternity Benefit Act, 1961 has been framed to provide maternity leave benefits to pregnant working women but till now for male professional there are no legal provisions for paternity leaves.

12. Rani and Selvarani (2011)

Stated that in IT companies there was a high degree of positive correlation between employees tasks at work and employees satisfaction where in work life balance acts as a mediators variable. In IT companies employees were provided with requisite opportunities to develop and enhance their knowledge and skills so that they are to undertake greater responsibility at work.

13. Rastogi and Bansal (2012)

Stated that because of the perception of gendered roles in Indian society support plays a significant role in the career decisions of Indian married working women. Spousal support for childcare and domestic chores helps the married women to sort out work life conflicts and concentrate on their career.

14. Morrison and Thurnell (2012)

Reported that flexible work hours where one would be able to begin and end at a flexible time was the widely accepted flexible work arrangement preferred by ninety percentage of male employees of a construction company.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN:

3.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Work-life balance which primarily deals with an employee's ability to properly priorities between work and his or her lifestyle, social life, health, family etc. is generally linked with employee productivity.

3.2 NEED OF THE STUDY:

The concept of work life quality focuses on researching and analysing the contents and processes implemented by management, providing employees with the best working life to improve organisational performance and meet the needs and requirements of workers.

3.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the system prevailing in Karanja industries Pvt. Ltd.
- To know how different department co-ordinate their functions to attain the departmental goals.
- To analyse the human relations prevailing in the organization.
- To know the technology implemented by the organization.
- To understand the perceptions of organizations with respect to work life balance.
- To analyse gender wise issues.
- To put forth suggestion to enhance work life balance quotient of organization.
- To trace the sector wise differences in the organizational initiatives for work life balance.

3.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- ⇒ Organization in "KARANJA INDUSTRIES PVT LTD" this study pertains to "Over View" of the organization this was conducted through visiting the organisation and observing all the functions for a ten week as a curriculum of MBA course.
- ⇒ The study helps to understand the various components of work life balance & its impact on organization.
- ⇒ It gives brief outline of workers employees satisfaction by the facilities provided to them in the company as well as in their social life.
- ⇒ If work life balance & its impact on organization is maintained, it provides the company then the employee turnover can be decreased.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In the study an attempt is made to evaluate the preface of the company. This study is made to know the organization of how it actually works in accordance with our perceived theoretical knowledge. This organizational study is conducted at KARANJA INDUSTRIES PVT. LTD, BIDAR.

Data Collection:

The purpose of conducting survey is really a difficult task. Data for the study is collected both from primary and secondary data.

Primary Data:

This data collected through discussion, interview, questionnaires were handed over to the respondents and their opinions were sought.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data means those data which are already available that is the data which has been already collected and analysed by someone else. This data was collected through company records, books, periodicals, manuals, karanja industries reports and their opinions were sought.

The research approach: survey method

The research instruments: the instruments used for the research are questionnaires.

The respondents: the employees of karanja industries

Sampling method: sampling method is a very important part of the research process. Sampling is the method of choosing unit from a residents of concern. Here, size of the sample is 50 employees and here technique used for this study is convenience sampling.

Convenience sampling: this is the method where the sample is chosen primarily on the basis of convenience of the researcher.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. From how many years you are working in this organisation.

Age	No, of respondents	Percentage
0 – 5 years	08	16
5 – 10 years	16	32
10 – 15 years	17	34
More than 15 years	09	18
TOTAL	50	100

ANALYSIS:

from the above table it is found that the how many years you are working in this organization response based in age is 0-5 years is 16%, 5-10 years is 32%, 10-15 years is 34% and more than 15 years are 18%.

INTERPRETATION:

The above table and graph shows majority of employees are working in this organization in age is 10-15 years is 34

2. Are you satisfied with the working hours of the organisation

Respondent Opinion	Respondents	Percentage
Yes	45	90
No	05	10
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS;

in the above table and graph found that 90% of employees satisfied and 10% of employees are not satisfied with the working hours of the organization.

INTERPRETATION:

The above table and graph shows majority of employees are strongly satisfied with the working hours of the organization.

3. Does after working hours you get enough time for your family

Respondents Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	42	84
No	08	16
Total	50	100

ANAYSIS:

from the above table and graph showing that does after working hours you get enough time for your family response based on time is 84% are yes and 16% are not get enough time for their family.

INTERPRETATION:

the above table and graph shows that majority 84% of employees get enough time for family after working hours.

4. Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life

Respondents Opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

from the above table and graph shows that the 80% of employees are able to balance their work life and 20% are feel that they are not able to balance the work life.

INTERPRETATION:

The majority of employees are feel that they are able to balance the work life is 80%.

5. Does the organisation take initiatives to manage work life of its employees

Respondent Opinion	No. of respondent	Percentage
Yes	35	70
No	15	30
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

the above table and graph shows that the organisation take initiative to manage work life of its employees is 70%, and the organisation does not take initiative to manage work life of its employees is 30%.

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table and graph shows that the majority of organization take initiative to manage work life of its employees is 70%.

6. If yes what are the initiatives your organisation has taken for managing work life

Respondent Opinion	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Provide flexible work things	25	50
Provide leaves to manage work life	15	30
Job share option is provided by the organisation	10	20
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

from the above table and graph shows that the organization taken initiative to provide flexible work life is 50%, the initiative taken by organization to provide leaves to manage work life is 30%, the initiative taken for job share option is provided by the organization for managing work life of employees.

INTERPRETATION:

from the above table and graph shows that majority of initiatives taken by organization to provide flexible work life is 50%.

7. Do you have more pressure of work in the organisation or it is evenly distributed

Respondent Opinion	No. of respondent	Percentage
Have Pressure	25	50
Work is evenly distributed	25	50
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

from the above table and graph shows that pressure of work in the organization or it is evenly distributed 50% are have pressure, 50% is evenly distributed.

INTERPRETATION:

from the above table and graph shows that work is evenly distributed 50% and have pressure of work in the organization is 50%.

8. Do you think policy for work life management helps to increase productivity of the organisation

Respondent Opinion	No. Of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	35	70
No	15	30
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

From the above table and graph shows that policy for work life management helps to increases productivity of the organization satisfied are 70%, and not satisfied is 30%.

INTERPRETATION:

from the above table and graph shows that majority policy for work life management helps to increases productivity of the organization is 70%.

9. Do you generally feel you are able to balance your work life due to work life management policy of the company

Respondent Opinion	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

From the above table and graph shows that employees generally feel they are able to balance work life due to work life management policy of the company is 80% and the employees are not able to balance their work life due to management policy of the company is 20%.

INTERPRETATION:

From the above table and graph shows that majority of employees able to balance work life due to management policy of the company is 80%.

10. Do you think with the efficient work life management policy organisation is able to retain its employees

Respondent Opinion	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	35	70
No	15	30
Total	50	100

ANALYSIS:

From the above table and graph shows that the efficient work life management policy organization is able to retain its employees says yes is 70% and employees says no is 30%.

INTERPRETATION:

from the above table and graph shows the majority of the efficient work life management policy organization is able to retain its employees is 70%.

5.1 FINDINGS

- The organization is one of the major industrial setups in bidar providing employment opportunities, it is spread in 85 acres of land including the lands and the manufacturing unit.
- More efforts are required in the marketing field and there is no recruitment in the company from last few years
- It offers employment to more than 506 no of employees at various levels and in different capacities and the mode of employment ranges from permanent contract to daily wages.
- Dealers are showing interest in purchasing the company's board because of high profit margin.
- Usage of modern technology.
- It is having centralized control system which is not useful for sudden decisions.
- Dealers are showing interest in purchasing the company's board because of high profit margin.
- They are having good and excellent infrastructure and ultra-structure facilities.
- The employees-employer relationship is very good.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS

Means communication should be made through telephone, internet, and websites and also through fax. Good means of combination system like transport facility should be made easy to deliver the goods in time.

- Keep the workers well contented and reduce labour turnover rate.
- Company has to improve its performance by reducing cost so that the company can able to achieve the profit in future.
- The company can introduce innovative quality practices to cut costs in various process of production and increase competitiveness in the market.
- Organization could re-design the structure as per the current environment to allow freedom and empower the management for decision making.
- Skills and motivation level of the employee can enhanced by providing effective training.
- To conclude company should minimize its overall cost and its operation for the benefit of the company.
- Effective, charismatic leadership is required who could steer the company towards profitability by controlling the leakage of available resources and overcoming the organizational weakness.
- The company had to capture local market to satisfy the local customers.s

6.CONCLUSION

The main objective of the in-plant training is to gain knowledge about functions of an organization, its back ground, nature of business, it's working and analysis of various product profile of the organization. Staying in the KARANJA PAPER MILL PVT LTD factory for almost a month was a platform for me to know its business conditions in the initial stage and gradual growth. The study helped me to view the process of producing various product produced in the factory. to know the performance of KARANJA PAPER MILL PVT LTD, produce good quality white cutting duplex paper board and kraft paper board. Workers are highly satisfied with and salary administration and welfare facilities. To conclude organizational study at KARANJA PAPER MILL PVT LTD. Helped me to relate the theoretical knowledge to the practical environment and enlightened me with the knowledge regarding.

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